

Supplementary: Quantifying Spatial Audio Quality Impairment

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A. DERIVATION OF THE OPTIMAL GAIN MATRIX

Denote the objective function to be minimized by

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{T}) = \sum_n \|\tilde{\mathbf{s}}[n] - \hat{\mathbf{s}}[n]\|^2 \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$= \sum_n (\tilde{\mathbf{s}}^T[n]\tilde{\mathbf{s}}[n] - 2\tilde{\mathbf{s}}^T[n]\hat{\mathbf{s}}[n] + \hat{\mathbf{s}}^T[n]\hat{\mathbf{s}}[n]). \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Taking the derivative with respect to \mathbf{A} gives

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial A_{ij}} = 2 \sum_n (\tilde{s}_i[n] - \hat{s}_i[n]) s_j[n - \tau_{ij}], \quad (\text{A.3})$$

since

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{s}_c[n]}{\partial A_{ij}} = \mathbb{I}[i = c] s_j[n - \tau_{ij}], \quad (\text{A.4})$$

where $\mathbb{I}[\cdot]$ is the Iverson bracket. By setting the derivative to zero, we have

$$\sum_n \hat{s}_i[n] s_j[n - \tau_{ij}] = \sum_n \tilde{s}_i[n] s_j[n - \tau_{ij}] \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$= \sum_d A_{id} \sum_n s_d[n - \tau_{id}] s_j[n - \tau_{ij}] \quad (\text{A.6})$$

which reduces to (5).

B. DERIVATION OF THE THEORETICAL SSR

For this section, let $\text{SSR} = 10 \log_{10} u$. Denote the mono reference signal by v . Let $E_v = \sum_n v^2[n]$. Considering only the necessary parametrization for III.A and III.B,

$$\hat{\mathbf{s}}[n] = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{g}_L v[n] \\ \hat{g}_R v[n - \hat{d}_R] \end{bmatrix}. \quad (\text{B.7})$$

Since all spatial error are theoretically accountable by (1), $\tilde{\mathbf{s}} \equiv \hat{\mathbf{s}}$. The reference signal is given by

$$\mathbf{s}[n] = \begin{bmatrix} g_L \\ g_R \end{bmatrix} \cdot v[n], \quad (\text{B.8})$$

and $E_{\mathbf{s}} = \sum_n \|\mathbf{s}[n]\|^2 = E_v$ since $g_L^2 + g_R^2 = 1$.

A. Panning Error

Where only panning error is present, $\hat{d}_R = 0$. Therefore,

$$u = \left(\sum_n \|\tilde{\mathbf{s}}[n] - \mathbf{s}[n]\|^2 \right)^{-1} \left(\sum_n \|\mathbf{s}[n]\|^2 \right) \quad (\text{B.9})$$

$$u^{-1} E_v = \sum_n \left\| \begin{bmatrix} \hat{g}_L - g_L \\ \hat{g}_R - g_R \end{bmatrix} \cdot v[n] \right\|^2 \quad (\text{B.10})$$

$$= [(\hat{g}_L - g_L)^2 + (\hat{g}_R - g_R)^2] \cdot E_v \quad (\text{B.11})$$

$$u^{-1} = 2 - 2 \cos \left(\frac{\pi}{4} (\hat{p} - p) \right). \quad (\text{B.12})$$

B. Panning and Delay Error

With $\hat{d}_R \neq 0$,

$$u^{-1} E_v = \sum_n \left\| \begin{bmatrix} (\hat{g}_L - g_L) v[n] \\ \hat{g}_R v[n - \hat{d}_R] - g_R v[n] \end{bmatrix} \right\|^2 \quad (\text{B.13})$$

$$= (\hat{g}_L - g_L)^2 E_v + \sum_n \left| \hat{g}_R v[n - \hat{d}_R] - g_R v[n] \right|^2 \quad (\text{B.14})$$

$$u^{-1} = (\hat{g}_L - g_L)^2 + (\hat{g}_R - g_R)^2 + \frac{2\hat{g}_R g_R}{E_v} \left[1 - \sum_n v[n - \hat{d}_R] v[n] \right] \quad (\text{B.15})$$

$$u^{-1} = 2 - 2 \cos \left(\frac{\pi}{4} (\hat{p} - p) \right) + 2\hat{g}_R g_R \left(1 - \frac{\kappa_v[-\hat{d}_R]}{\kappa_v[0]} \right), \quad (\text{B.16})$$

where $\kappa_v[\cdot]$ is the autocorrelation function of v . Since $|\kappa_v[d]| \leq \kappa_v[0]$ for all d , we have

$$0 \leq u^{-1} - 2 - 2 \cos \left(\frac{\pi}{4} (\hat{p} - p) \right) \leq 4\hat{g}_R g_R. \quad (\text{B.17})$$

C. ADDITIONAL EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fig. A1. SSR and SRR of the test signals compressed by AAC, by operating mode and average bitrates.

Fig. A2. SSR and SRR of the test signals compressed by Opus, by operating mode and constant bitrates.